

A Comparative Study of Efficient In-Orbit Model Updating Methods

P. del Hoyo¹, N. Vallez¹, and O. Deniz¹

VISILAB, ETS Ingeniería Industrial, Ciudad Real, UCLM, Spain
{pablo.delhoyo,noelia.vallez,oscar.deniz}@uclm.es

Abstract. Updating a neural network running on an edge device can be quite challenging, especially when the device uses a low bandwidth uplink communication channel. For that reason, sending all the model weights becomes prohibitive. An example of such a device is an Earth Observation (EO) satellite, which employs Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to make decisions related to the images captured using its EO sensors. A possible approach to efficiently update these kinds of devices is to leverage the fact that the weights which are currently used by the edge device are known and update only a subset of them. In this work, several criteria for choosing the subset of weights which are updated have been compared. Since our main focus is to efficiently update models running on EO satellites, the datasets which have been used to test the methods correspond to images taken by these kinds of satellites. The results show that the best approach is Deep Partial Update (DPU). Specifically, the fully fine-tuned model achieves a Dice score of 0.6641 but if DPU is applied in a setting where 25 % the weights are allowed to change, the partially updated model gives a Dice score of 0.6391.

Keywords: Network Update · Edge AI · Bandwidth-Constrained Devices · Model Adaptation.

1 Introduction

One of the many challenges in deploying deep learning models is to efficiently update them when the distribution of the data seen by the deployed model becomes different from the one used to train it. The most straightforward approach to address this issue is to retrain the model using samples from the new distribution and then deploy it again. However, updating all the weights of a model running on a device with a low bandwidth uplink communication channel can be time consuming because the number of parameters which have to be sent are in the order of millions.

An example of a device whose communication channel is bandwidth-constrained is an Earth Observation (EO) satellite. For example, many small satellites employ the S band, whose uplink bandwidth is limited to a few kbps [9]. These kinds of satellites are equipped with EO sensors in charge of capturing images of the Earth's surface, among other kinds of information. These satellites include neural networks models which, for example, decide which images are worth sending

to Earth ground stations. For instance, if an image does not provide useful information because they are cloudy, then sending them would consume bandwidth unnecessarily. Additionally, neural network-based models can be used to monitor certain areas or objects in real-time. For example, monitoring of maritime vessels makes it possible to detect activities such as illegal fishing [11].

When a new EO sensor is deployed, there are no images captured by it because it has not been in orbit. As a consequence, the neural network in charge of running inferences on the images taken by the new EO sensor cannot be trained with samples of the types of images which are going to encounter once it is deployed. The neural network can be trained on images taken by a different sensor, but the performance when it is deployed is likely to be worse than the one estimated after the training process if, for example, the configuration of the sensor has changed. Once enough images have been gathered from the new sensor, a new model is trained and the resulting weights are sent to the satellite considering that the uplink channel bandwidth is limited. Additionally, the satellite’s classification task may change, requiring an update.

In this work, several existing techniques which try to minimize the size of the update (reducing the amount of weights sent) while minimizing the model performance degradation in the context of neural networks running on EO satellites have been compared.

2 Previous work

In [14], two methods, which are collectively referred as Efficient Network Update (ENU), were used to reduce the size of the weight update. For their experiments, which involved classifying images into a fixed set of categories, two datasets were used: the Diabetic Retinopathy 2015 dataset and the APTOS 2019 Blindness Detection dataset. The former acted as the dataset used to train the model when image samples from another distribution are still not available and the latter is the dataset with which they want to train the model, which we will refer to as the “target dataset”. After training the model on the Diabetic Retinopathy 2015 dataset and obtaining the “pretrained model”, they applied different forms of fine-tuning to adapt it to the target dataset. Since the weights that change during fine-tuning are the ones that need to be updated, the two approaches establish a procedure to select those that will not change. One of them, ENU-Consecutive, freezes the last l layers of the model architecture, where l is the minimum number of layers whose total number of parameters is at least n , which represents the number of parameters the user wants to freeze. Normally, n is calculated from a percentage over the total number of parameters given by the user. In this method, the greater the value of n , the better the performance. However, this incurs in a larger update size. For the other method, ENU-Selective, all the parameters of the pretrained model are fine-tuned on the target dataset, resulting in a fully fine-tuned model. Afterwards, the difference between the pretrained model and the fully fine-tuned model is computed layer-wise. Specifically, the difference is calculated using the mean absolute difference. Then, the layers are

sorted in ascending order, and the first l layers are selected, where l is the minimum number of layers whose total number of parameters is at least n . Finally, the pretrained model is fine-tuned again on the target dataset. Nevertheless, this time, the previously selected l layers are frozen. As with the previous method, n is calculated from a percentage over the total number of parameters and also represents a trade-off between the weight update size and the model's performance. The experiments carried out by the authors suggest that, for a similar weight update size, the models obtained using the ENU-Selective procedure were better than ones obtained using the ENU-Consecutive approach. However, even though the proposed methods were developed to efficiently update a neural network running in a EO satellite, the selected datasets were unrelated to the types of images captured by these kinds of devices. A depiction of the weight selection process performed by both ENU approaches is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Example of the weight selection performed both ENU approaches
Image obtained from [14]

Additionally, graphical representation of the process of partially updating a model is shown in Figure 2. The idea of selecting the weights to be sent as the ones that vary the most is also applied in [10] to efficiently update a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model running on IoT devices without changing its architecture. They select a parameter of the new model if it is above a certain threshold which depends on the layer where the weight is located. To choose this threshold, several values are tested, and the one that results in the smallest number of weight updates without degrading the performance of the fully fine-tuned model is selected. The same idea of partially updating a neural network is applied by the authors of [13]. However, in this case, they select the weights to be frozen based on a criterion that, under certain assumptions, minimizes the upper bound of the difference between the loss of the fully fine-tuned model and the loss of the partially updated model. This method is called Deep Partial Update (DPU).

Fig. 2: Process of partially updating a model running on the satellite

(a) First, when the satellite is on Earth, all the model weights are uploaded there without being subject to bandwidth constraints. (b) When the model running on the satellite needs to be updated, only the weights which have changed need to be sent

Instead of reducing the number of parameters sent to the satellite, some authors propose sending all parameters incrementally. This is done every time the communication with the satellite from ground stations is possible, which, in the case of Low Earth Orbit satellites such as CubeSat, lasts around ten minutes and only happens four or five times a day [15]. However, this is done in such a way that the performance degradation of running a partially updated model is reduced. As more parameters are received, the performance will consistently improve until all weights have been transmitted [9].

Other kinds of methods fall under the category of Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT). They aim at reducing the computational and memory costs of fine-tuning a model. These kinds of methods have received much attention as a consequence of the huge size of Large Language Models (LLMs), whose parameter count is in the order of billions [4]. One of the most popular PEFT approaches is called Low Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [7]. LoRA is normally applied to dense layers. The method constrains the weight update ΔW experienced by a weight matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times k}$ by forcing it to be low-rank. Specifically, $\Delta W = BA$ where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times k}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$ and $r \ll \min(a, b)$ is the rank. During fine-tuning, all parameters are frozen except for those introduced by this method.

This method can also be used in convolutional layers by appropriately reshaping the convolution filter, as it is done in [2].

Additionally, there exist other techniques which try to reduce the computational cost of running neural network-based models. These are especially relevant when the model has to be deployed on resource-constrained devices, such as mobile phones. One of those techniques, named quantization, converts high-precision number representations to low-precision ones [12]. As a consequence, the size of the model weights is reduced, and the inference speed is increased. Another well-known technique for model compression is called pruning [6]. It consists of removing the parts of the model that have little influence on the final output. The two most used approaches for applying pruning to a neural network-based model are unstructured pruning and structured pruning. The former sets the least important neurons and weights to zero. Although this can lead to a considerable shrinkage in the model size, the approach results in sparse matrix operations, which are generally slow [3]. Because of that inconvenience, structured pruning removes bigger parts of the network at once, such as channels in a convolutional layer, which maintain the dense matrices of the model. However, the rate at which performance degradation occurs is faster because the removal of weights is coarser. Another approach to model compression is known as knowledge distillation. It works by training a teacher model that is then used to train a student model. The teacher model is larger than the student model. The training of the latter uses the "soft" probabilities produced by the former, since they give more information than the "hard" probabilities [5]. All of these techniques are orthogonal to partially updating a model because they can be used in addition to it to reduce the size of the parameter update. However, care must be taken to avoid a significant drop in performance.

3 Methods and materials

In this work, several methods have been tested to reduce the size of the weight update needed to be sent to an EO satellite to adapt its neural network-based model to samples from a distribution different than the one used to train it. The methods have been tested on a binary semantic segmentation task using the U-Net neural network architecture. We first trained the U-Net on the ship segmentation dataset HRSC2016-MS Dataset [1] (Fig. 3a). This is assumed to be the initial model which is uploaded to the device and is not subject to bandwidth constraints. Then, the initial model is fine-tuned on another ship segmentation dataset released by Airbus for a ship detection challenge [8] (Fig. 3b). This corresponds to the updated model which must be transmitted the EO satellite. However, since the EO satellite has a low uplink bandwidth communication channel, only some of the weights of the fine-tuned model will be sent. The tested methods use different criteria to choose those weights, given the number of parameters the user wants to send. In the case of LoRA, we assume that the fine-tuned model is the pretrained one with some adapter matrices learned from the fine-tuning dataset.

(a) HRSC2016-MS dataset sample image used to train the initial model (b) Airbus Ship Detection sample image used to train the updated model

Fig. 3: Sample images from the datasets used.

One of the tested methods consists of freezing the weights that vary the least, which is exactly one of the criteria the authors of DPU [13] used. This can be seen as a refinement of the technique named ENU-Selective, which was described in the previous section. This is because ENU-Selective freezes all the parameters in the selected layers instead of freezing at the parameter level, as DPU does. In this work, the variation of a parameter across different models is calculated as the absolute difference between them.

Another method which has been tested is LoRA. Since the chosen neural network architecture consists of convolution and deconvolution operations but LoRA is applied to dense layers, the challenge of this approach lies in how to adapt it to the layers that perform those convolutions. Given a convolution filter $W \in \mathbb{R}^{c_{out} \times c_{in} \times k \times k}$, where k is the kernel size, c_{in} is the number of input channels and c_{out} is the number of output channels, we follow the same approach as the authors of LoRA. If $W_{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{c_{out} \times c_{in} \times k \times k}$, then the variation ΔW is represented as the product of $B \in \mathbb{R}^{c_{out} \cdot k \times r}$ and $A \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times c_{in} \times k}$ which results in the matrix $BA \in \mathbb{R}^{c_{out} \cdot k \times c_{in} \cdot k}$. Finally, BA is reshaped into the shape of W_0 so that it can be added to it. The adapter matrices are only applied if the number of elements of BA is less than the number of parameters in W_0 . This method has been tested in two different ways: in one of them, the adapters have been added only to the convolutional layers and in the other, the adapters have been added to both convolutional and deconvolutional layers.

Finally, both ENU-Consecutive and ENU-Selective methods have also been tested to see how they compare with the ones which have been mentioned above.

4 Results

In Table 1, the performance of partially updated models obtained applying different methods and the proportion of weights which have changed are shown. This proportion is shown because the number of parameters which vary are the ones which have to be sent to the satellite. This type of data is the one which mainly contributes to the size of the weight update message and, consequently, to bandwidth consumption. In addition to that, the results obtained by applying LoRA to both the convolutional and deconvolutional layers and only to the convolutional layers using different ranks are shown in Table 2. Since we are testing the methods in a binary semantic segmentation task, the performance metric used is the Dice score. The score reported in this work is computed as the average of the Dice score of three models trained and tested on three different random partitions of the same dataset. These results are also shown in Figure 4. For comparison, the Dice score obtained for the fully fine-tuned model, which represents the updated model, is 0.6641. Ideally, the performance of the compared methods should achieve a similar score or show only a small decrease.

Method	Changed weights %	Dice score	Full-finetuned deviation
ENU-Consecutive	69.70%	0.5165 ± 0.0298	22.22 %
ENU-Consecutive	39.29%	0.4785 ± 0.0158	-27.94 %
ENU-Consecutive	17.32%	0.4089 ± 0.0223	-38.42 %
ENU-Selective	70.60%	0.6191 ± 0.0345	-6.77 %
ENU-Selective	40.20%	0.6242 ± 0.0286	-6.00 %
ENU-Selective	23.09%	0.5727 ± 0.0263	-13.76 %
DPU	75%	0.6328 ± 0.0157	-4.71 %
DPU	50%	0.6396 ± 0.0157	-3.68 %
DPU	25%	0.6391 ± 0.0174	-3.76 %

Table 1: Performance of partially updated models using the methods ENU- Consecutive, ENU-Selective and DPU

As it can be seen in the table, the method which achieves the best performance with the least number of changed weights is DPU. In fact, as we increase the number of weights which are allowed to change, the performance does not

Rank	Changed weights (%)	Dice score	Deconvolution
214	68.46%	0.5974 ± 0.0036	No
80	35.03%	0.5833 ± 0.0287	No
30	19.15%	0.5864 ± 0.0129	No
214	65.94%	0.5849 ± 0.0326	Yes
80	28.93%	0.5779 ± 0.0383	Yes
30	11.29%	0.5681 ± 0.0129	Yes

Table 2: Performance of models updated using LoRA. Changed weights (%) represents the percentage of parameters that change relative to the total. The deconvolution column indicates whether the adapters have been applied to the deconvolution layers.

seem to improve. The next best method is ENU-Selective, which is not surprising given that DPU is the best performing method since DPU is a refinement of ENU-Selective. Additionally, the obtained results are consistent with the ones the authors of both ENU methods published, in which their results showed that ENU-Selective outperformed ENU-Consecutive.

On the other hand, the results obtained indicate that LoRA is worse than partially updating the neural network using ENU-Selective or DPU. This might be because the adapter matrices do not respect the structure of a convolution operation because the way in which LoRA is applied to a convolutional kernel is by performing reshaping operations. However, as the number of parameters allowed to change increases, the performance metric also increases, which is something to be expected.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

In this work we have compared several methods which enable updating a neural network running on a device without having to transfer the weights of the fully updated model. The methods have been tested on a binary semantic segmentation task with EO images. The results obtained suggest that the Deep Partial Updating (DPU) method is the one which achieves the best performance with the smallest model update size.

Future investigations could explore how other methods, such as quantization, can be used in combination with techniques based on the same underlying principle as DPU to further reduce the size of the weight update without severely

Fig. 4: Plot of the performance of each model vs the percentage of weights which have changed

compromising model performance. Additionally, methods which do not rely on partially updating the model are also worth exploring.

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References

1. Chen, W., Han, B., Yang, Z., Gao, X.: Mssdet: Multi-scale ship-detection framework in optical remote-sensing images and new benchmark. *Remote Sensing* **14**(21), 5460 (2022)
2. Ding, C., Cao, X., Xie, J., Fan, L., Wang, S., Lu, Z.: LoRA-C: Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning of Robust CNN for IoT Devices. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.16954* (2024)
3. Eun-Jin, I.: Optimizing the performance of sparse matrix vector multiplication. Ph. D. thesis, Univ. of California (2000)
4. Fu, Z., Yang, H., So, A.M.C., Lam, W., Bing, L., Collier, N.: On the effectiveness of parameter-efficient fine-tuning. In: *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*. vol. 37, pp. 12799–12807 (2023)
5. Gou, J., Yu, B., Maybank, S.J., Tao, D.: Knowledge distillation: A survey. *International Journal of Computer Vision* **129**(6), 1789–1819 (2021)

6. Hohman, F., Kery, M.B., Ren, D., Moritz, D.: Model compression in practice: Lessons learned from practitioners creating on-device machine learning experiences. In: Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. pp. 1–18 (2024)
7. Hu, E.J., Shen, Y., Wallis, P., Allen-Zhu, Z., Li, Y., Wang, S., Wang, L., Chen, W.: LoRA: Low-rank adaptation of large language models. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.09685 (2021)
8. inversion, Faudi, J., Martin: Airbus ship detection challenge. <https://kaggle.com/competitions/airbus-ship-detection> (2018), kaggle
9. Kondrateva, O., Dietzel, S., Scheuermann, B.: Quantority: Parameter prioritization for incremental updates of convolutional neural networks in small satellite missions. In: 2024 IFIP Networking Conference (IFIP Networking). pp. 341–349. IEEE (2024)
10. Liu, D., Yang, C., Li, S., Chen, X., Ren, J., Liu, R., Duan, M., Tan, Y., Liang, L.: FitCNN: A cloud-assisted and low-cost framework for updating CNNs on IoT devices. *Future generation computer systems* **91**, 277–289 (2019)
11. Marin, A., Coelho, C., Deconinck, F., Babkina, I., Longepe, N., Pastena, M.: Phi-Sat-2: Onboard ai apps for earth observation. *Proc. Space Artif. Intell* **6** (2021)
12. Nagel, M., Fournarakis, M., Amjad, R.A., Bondarenko, Y., Van Baalen, M., Blankevoort, T.: A white paper on neural network quantization. arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.08295 (2021)
13. Qu, Z., Liu, C., Thiele, L.: Deep Partial Updating: Towards Communication Efficient Updating for On-device Inference. In: European Conference on Computer Vision. pp. 137–153. Springer (2022)
14. Vallez, N., Rodriguez-Bobada, R., Dunne, A., Espinosa-Aranda, J.L.: Efficient In-Orbit CNN Updates. In: 2023 European Data Handling & Data Processing Conference (EDHPC). pp. 1–5. IEEE (2023)
15. Vasisht, D., Shenoy, J., Chandra, R.: L2d2: Low latency distributed downlink for LEO satellites. In: Proceedings of the 2021 ACM SIGCOMM 2021 Conference. pp. 151–164 (2021)